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DEVELOPMENT OF DRAFT RIVER BASIN MANAGEMENT PLAN FOR THE DANUBE-PRUT AND BLACK SEA DISTRICT IN REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

2022-2027

Thematic summary

Chisinau, 2023

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Agency „Apele Moldovei”

Responsible EU member state consortium EUWI+ project leader

Mr Alexander Zinke, Umweltbundesamt GmbH (AT)

EUWI+ country representative in Moldova

Mr Victor Bujac

Responsible international thematic lead expert

Pierre Henry de Villeneuve, Office International de l'Eau

Responsible national thematic lead expert

Bejan Iurie, OIKUMENA Public Association

Authors: Iurii Bejan, Petru Bacal, Tudor Castravet, Vitalie Dilan, Lucia Capatina, Nicolae

Boboc, Boris Iurciuc, Natalia Zgîrcu, Viorica Angheluta, Pavel Tîtu, Liliana

Stratan, Vladimir Mogîldea, Jechiu Iradion, OIKUMENA Public Association

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Spittelauer Lände 5 **21/23 rue de Madrid**

1090 Vienna, Austria **75008 Paris, France**

Responsible IOW Communication officer:

Ms Chloé Déchelette c.dechelette@oieau.fr

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ACRONYMS

AGRM	Agency for Geology and Mineral Resources
BOD	Biological Oxygen Demand
BQE	Biological Quality Element
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
CORINE	Coordination of Information on the Environment
DPBS RBD	Danube-Prut and Black Sea River Basin District
EHGeoM	Moldavian Hydrogeological Expedition
EUWI+	European Union Water Initiative Plus for the Eastern Partnership
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GWB	Groundwater Body
HMWB	Heavily Modified Water Body
HPP	Hydropower Plant
MARDE	Ministry of Agriculture, Regional Development and Environment
PoM	Programme of Measures
RBD	River Basin District
RBMP	River Basin Management Plan
SHS	State Hydrometeorological Service
SWB	Surface Water Body
TAU	Territorial Administrative Units
WFD	Water Framework Directive

1. CHARACTERISATION OF THE DANUBE-PRUT AND BLACK SEA RIVER BASIN DISTRICT

1.1. NATURAL CONDITIONS IN THE RIVER BASIN DISTRICT

Location and geographic overview:

The total catchment area of the Danube-Prut and Black Sea River Basin District (DPBS RBD) is 14,770 km² within the borders of the Republic of Moldova, which represents 43.6% of the country's total area. From the administrative-territorial perspective, DPBS RBD includes 18 administrative rayons. From North to South, the district extends over approximately 350 km, with variable width (from 25 km to 120 km). The geographical position and configuration of the district determine a remarkable diversity of geological structure, geomorphologic characteristics and climate conditions. The specifics of these environmental components determine, significantly, the characteristics of the biota, soils, hydrological and hydro-chemical characteristics of the ground and surface waters. The average value of the absolute altitude of the district landscape is 142 m, a typical value for the lowland regions.

The Prut hydrographic basin is part of the Danube river basin, representing its eastern border. The Danube river basin crosses the territory of 19 European countries. The Republic of Moldova is a member of the International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River and directly manages 0.94% of its total area. The Prut river basin is situated on the territory of three countries (fig. 1), 28% in the Republic of Moldova (39% in Romania and 33% in Ukraine) of the total area of 27,540 km².

Figure 1. The transboundary Danube-Prut and Black Sea River Basin District

Climate:

The DPBS RBD has a continental climate featuring short, mild winters with little snow, long summers and reduced humidity. *Atmospheric precipitations* are the most important element in the formation of water reserves in DPBS RBD, the structure of the hydrographical network and, to a certain extent, of the water quality. The distribution of the annual average rainfall in the DPBS RBD, over the period of 1980-2017, is generally characterised by a spatially differentiated distribution, with 616 mm in the north (Briceni meteorological station) and 506 mm in the south (Comrat station). *Air temperature* is a key element of climatic conditions and has an impact on the entire hydrographical district. It is determined directly by solar radiation and atmospheric circulation. The annual average values during the 1980 - 2017 period are respectively 8.1 °C in Briceni (Northern part) and, 10.8 °C in Cahul (Southern part).

Flora:

The natural vegetation is predominantly represented by steppe associations (14.7%) and forests (9.5%). The composition and spatial distribution of the vegetation are determined by the zonal and azonal areas of the DPBS RBD.

In the Northern region of the Prut basin, in the North Moldavian Plateau and in the middle half of the Middle Prut Plate, especially on the interfluvial peaks, there are forest landscapes, represented by cherry oak forests, wild apple trees, solitary maple, yew, hornbeam. In the floodplain of the isolated Prut, meadow forests are preserved. In the forests' ecosystems in the south of the district, there are representatives of the Mediterranean fluffy oaks (*Quercus pubescens*), which is the north-eastern boundary of the area with fluffy oak forests.

The lower Prut lakes region is included in the List of Wetlands of International Importance, as Ramsar area No. 1029 "Lower Prut Lakes" (especially as a habitat for aquatic birds).

Land Cover:

Land cover of DPBS RBD was analysed using recent Landsat imagery classification of 30 m resolution. Land cover was classified using the second Level of CORINE system (table 1 and fig. 2). The operational structure of the modality of land use within the district changes from North to South. In the northern part the lands are used as agri-forest and agri-pastures. Within the limits of the Codri Plateau the landscape features forest-vine-orchards, while arable land dominates towards South.

Table 1. Land Cover Type Distribution within DPBS RBD

Land Cover Type	Area, km ²	Percentage, %
Arable land	8,441.3	57.7
Pastures and grasslands	2,157.7	14.7
Forests	1,385.2	9.4
Vineyards	859.2	5.9
Orchards	257.2	1.8
Water	273.4	1.9
Urban areas	1262	8.6

Figure 2. Land Cover Types Distribution within DPBS RBD

Natural Hazards:

Hydrological and geodynamic risks with a higher frequency include floods, landslides and erosion, processes generated by the position of the district in the temperate zone, with the region of the Prut hydrographical basin, located in the area of the Eastern Carpathians. Research shows a twofold increase in flood frequency over the last 40 to 50 years, compared to the previous one hundred years. The Prut river basin is the most exposed area to flood risk in the entire DPBS RBD.

Floods in the Prut River Basin are mostly generated by heavy rains that commonly occur in the basin mountain sector, as recorded, for example, in 1988, 2008, 2010. Significant flood events were recorded in the second half of the twentieth century and the first decade of the 21st century (1959, 1965, 1969, 1970, 1971, 1975, 1991, 1996, 1998, 2008 and 2010).

On small water courses, heavy torrential rains in some years cause flash floods as recorded, for example, in June 2016 on the Lunga River in Ceadar-Lunga. The floods in the lower course of the Prut river, during the summer period, are generated by the high levels of the Danube, which, due to the reclamation phenomenon, lead to the blocking of the Prut's waters. Thus, as an example, on 7 July 2010, during extensive flooding in the lower Prut River, the Danube water level at Galati Station reached 581 cm, a value that exceeded the historical maximum, registered on 26 April 2006.

The entire Prut River is characterised by a high flood risk in the Prut valley, with more extensive areas in the Criva – Lipcani-Drepcauti (upstream Costesti-Stinca reservoir), Movileni - Pruteni, Zagarancea - Ungheni, Nemteni - Cotul Morii – Obileni, Gotesti – Ghioltosu, Cahul – Rosu (downstream Costesti-Stinca reservoir) due to the poor conditions of dykes. Areas of the rivers with medium flood risk are much more extensive, they almost fully occupy the courses of the small and medium rivers and the majority of the Prut river meadow.

1.2. SURFACE WATER RESOURCES

The surface water resources of the Prut River are evaluated based on the database of the monitoring network of SHS of Moldova. The average annual flow volume of the Prut River is equal to 2.7 km³, and varies from 1.2 km³ in years with insufficient humidity up to 5 km³, values achieved in the years with heavy rainfall. The average annual flow is equal to 78 - 94 m³/s, fluctuations range from 40 up to 162 m³/s (table 2 and fig. 3).

Table 2. The parameters of surface water in the Prut River, Moldova

Quantitative characteristics	Prut River water resources at stations				
	Sirauti	Costesti HPP	Ungheni	Leova	Prut mouth
Catchment area, km ²	9230	11800	15200	23400	27540
Annual averages:					
Discharge, in m ³ /s	77.7	83.0	86.7	90.8	93.7
Specific discharge, in l/s*km ²	8.42	7.03	5.71	3.88	3.40
Flow, in mm	266	222	180	122	107

Information about water resources on tributaries of the Prut River within the limits of the Republic of Moldova is insufficient due to the lack of monitoring data. Relatively comprehensive data exist only for six tributaries. The multiannual average flow of Prut River tributaries ranges from 1.21 m³/s (Girila Mare) to 2.64 m³/s (Camenca). The largest volume of water is characteristic for the river Camenca, exceeding 83.38 mln. m³ and the lowest - 10 mln. m³ - for Girila Mare. Table 3 shows the estimated values for the main tributaries of the Prut within the territory of Moldova.

Figure 3. Flow monitoring network on the Prut river

Table 3. Water resources of the main tributaries of the Prut river
(in the limits of Moldova)

Tributary	Length, km	Catchment area, km ²	Specific discharge, l/s/km ²	Annual flow volume, mil. m ³	Code
Vilia	50	298	2.3	21.40	MD1116
Lopatnic	57	265	2.3	16.00	MD1116
Racovt	67	795	2.3	57.40	MD1115
Draghiste	70.7	279	2.04	17.97	-
Ciuhur	90	724	1.93	60.86	MD1114
Camenca	93	1230	2.64	83.38	MD1113
Caldarusu	40	318	1.87	58.93	MD1112
Glodeanca	30	147	1.3	41.00	-
Girila Mare	40	285	1.21	10.72	MD1110
Delia	30	219	1.62	51.08	MD1109
Nyrnova	49	358	1.66	18.79	MD1106
Lapusna	70	483	1.64	24.91	MD1105
Sarata	59	716	1.2	27.12	MD1104
Tigheci	43	205	1.8	11.67	MD1103
Larga (2)	33	150	1.8	8.50	MD1102

The surface water resources of the Danube – Black Sea basin are rather modest (table 4). The region features only about 1% of the all available surface water resources of the country.

Table 4. Water resources of the rivers in the Danube-Black Sea reference area

Tributary	Length, km	Basin area, km ²	The annual average flow, m ³ /s	Specific average flow, l/s/km ²	Annual average flow, mil.m ³ /year	Code
Cahul	44.8	577.9	0.27	0.46	8.5	MD1201
Salcia Mare	30.1	563.2	0.20	0.31	6.3	-
Ialpug	113.3	1595.5	0.64	0.4	20.0	MD1202
Lunga	77.5	1030.0	0.30	0.26	9.5	-
Lunguta	48.5	173.6	0.50	0.27	1.6	-
Cogilnic	104.2	1031.1	0.70	0.63	22.1	MD1301
Saca	12.2	30.5	0.02	0.56	0.6	-
Ceaga	17.8	339.9	0.20	0.53	0.63	-
Sarata	19.4	101.3	0.03	0.3	0.95	MD1302
Copceac	23.2	112.9	0.04	0.32	1.3	-
Bebei	27.2	178.6	0.06	0.31	1.9	-
Hadjider	7.8	201.9	0.06	0.28	1.9	MD1303
Caplani	17.9	123.6	0.04	0.29	1.26	-
Total		6060			76.54	

1.3. GROUNDWATER RESOURCES

Following hydrogeological prospects, total groundwater reserves were estimated to be 3,478.9 m³/day on 01.01.2014. The area between Prut and Dniester is a complex aquifer, in which aquifers and water horizons are interconnected. At present, the study and exploitation of groundwater for drinking and technical water supply is carried out in the following aquifers:

- The aquifer horizon of the alluvial deposits of the meadows and river terraces - a, adA₃;
- The aquifer complex of alluvial deposits - aN₂-A₁₋₂;
- The pontian aquifer set - N₂p;

- The aquifer complex of the Superior-Meotian Sarmatian - bN_1S_3-m ;
- The aquifer complex of the Middle Sarmatian deposits (Basarabian) (Congerian horizon) - N_1s_2 ;
- The Badenian-Sarmatian aquifer complex - N_1b-S_{1+2} ;
- The Silurian-Cretaceous aquifer complex - K-S.

1.4. DRIVING FORCES

Population and Demography

Demographic analysis is conducted based on the data obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics (<http://statistica.gov.md>).

The total population of DPBS RBD is 1,025,300 inh., which represents 36.5% of the country's population. The district territory is a typical rural area, and about 76% of the population lives in the rural area. The average density of the population in the district is 69.4 inh./km². In the last 25 years the population in the basin has decreased to about 67 thousand inhabitants. The size of towns, by size of population, varies from about 2 thousand inh. (towns of Cornesti and Costesti) up to 30,8 thousand inh. (town of Ungheni) (fig. 4). The average size of towns is 10,6 thousand inh. The rural population represents about 790.5 thousand inh. and is concentrated in 634 villages. The size of villages varies from 9 inh. (v. Popovca, Cantemir rayon) up to 11,123 inh. (v. Congaz, TAU Gagauzia). The average village size is 1,231 inh. In total, there are 12 localities with a population of over 10,0 thousand inh. and 126 localities with a population between 2,0 thousand and 10,0 thousand.

Taking into consideration the evolution of the main demographic indicators, the region is subject to a noticeable decreasing trend in population. This trend is likely to continue unless essential progress is made in the economic development of towns. This context of reduced population and preservation of the current level of economic development is likely to lead to a decrease of the human pressure on water resources and a stagnation in the amount of water consumed.

Agriculture

Agriculture is a traditional branch of the economy of the Republic of Moldova. The agri-food sector currently ensures about 25% of the total GDP value and engages now about 1/3 of the active population. The high share of arable land (57.7%) within DPBS RBD, the domination of hoed crops in the structure of seeded surfaces (over 90%) and the intense use of chemical fertilizers (average 52 kg/ha), cause intensive contamination of water resources with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, clogging of the surface water, as well as other negative processes.

In recent years, the Republic of Moldova has implemented the large-scale rehabilitation and expansion of irrigation systems. Within DPBS RBD there are 37 centralised irrigation systems. Most of these require rehabilitation. The total surface area designed for irrigation is 52,0 thousand ha, of which about 11,0 thousand ha have been rehabilitated.

Fish farming

The total surface of the natural fishing basins fund of R. Moldova represents 9,570 ha; within the limits of DPBS RBD the following are found:

- ✓ *The Manta marshes* – surface – 2,2 thousand ha, dominating depths – 1-3 m. Almost all marsh surfaces include pits for wintering fish and over 750 ha of spawning spots (places for laying or depositing eggs), with a depth varying between 0.5 and 1 m. The main species of fish are: carp, bream, crucian, roach;
- ✓ *The Beleu Lake* (now part of the scientific reservation “Lower Prut”), surface – 950 ha, depths vary between 0.5-3 m, surface spawning places represent 350 ha;
- ✓ *The Prut River*, within the limits of the territory of the Republic of Moldova has a surface of 2,6 thousand ha. The main fish species: bream, crucian, pike, carp, catfish;
- ✓ *The Costesti – Stanca* reservoir, within the limits of the territory of the Republic of Moldova, with a surface of 2,5 thousand ha, average depth 10 m, is a multiple use water body including some fish farming. The main fish species: bream, roach, hake, zander, crucian, rapacious carp.

Hydropower Plants (HPPs)

Within DPBS RBD there is only one hydro power plant – Costesti-Stanca. The power is exploited by 2 plants with an aggregate of 16 MW (for each part – Moldavian and Romanian) at a flow rate of $2 \times 65 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$, with an average annual power of $2 \times 65 \text{ GWh}$. Electricity production is distributed equally between R. Moldova and Romania.

Mining

Mineral deposits are predominant among construction materials. In the DPBS RBD there are 22 quarries (sand, clay and limestone). The impact of mining on water resources is particularly high. The extraction of mineral raw materials using the “latest” method (quarries) causes perforation of groundwater bodies, which respectively lowers water levels in nearby rivers, wells, springs etc. Extraction of sand and gravel (silt) from the river meadows (especially from the Prut River meadow in the limit of Glodeni, Ungheni, Cahul rayons etc.) has many negative consequences: decrease in water level, increase in water slope, increase in river course rate, etc.

Industry

The highest water abstractions from the Prut River are recorded in the most populated rayons and, respectively, the most industrialised ones – Edinet (sugar factories), Ungheni and Cahul (beverage productions).

Tourism

Tourism is a perspective branch in the sustainable use of natural and anthropogenic resources existing in the area of the basin. Potential exists for rural, ecological, cultural, spa and viti-vinicol tourism.

1.5. THE RIVER BASIN IN THE FUTURE

The main priorities of the territorial development strategy for DPBS RBD are:

- 1) Adapting water consumption to climate change and diminishing surface water resources.
- 2) Expanding aquatic ecosystems, including wetlands.
- 3) Extending the aqueduct, sewage and sewage network.

Figure 4. Watershed Area of DPBS RBD

2. PRESSURES AND IMPACTS OF HUMAN ACTIVITIES

2.1. WATER USE

Water abstraction and allocation in the DPBS RBD are carried out for household drinking, agricultural (mainly irrigation) and industrial purposes. From 2007-2017, an annual average of 33.7 million m³ of water was abstracted in the DPBS RBD. Over 60% (21.1 million m³) of abstracted water comes from groundwater sources. Thus, the volume of abstracted and used water is determined by the surface of these rayons and by size of its urban centres, as well as by the volume of water used for agriculture and household purposes (fig. 5). Basically, all

of the water used in agriculture for specific consumption is only very partially returned to the water basins and is attributed to losses.

In the last 10 years, there has been a decrease in the volume of captured water, especially from surface sources (fig. 6).

The average water supply tariff in the DPBS RBD is, on average, 17.2 MDL/m³. Tariffs for public water supply are, on average, 11.5 MDL/m³. Water supplying tariffs for the economic agents were, on average, 35.8 MDL/m³ in 2018.

Figure 5. Water abstraction in DPBS RBD
(annual average 2007-2017)

Source: Annual Reports (2007-2017) on the Indices of water management. "Apele Moldovei" Agency

Figure 6. Dynamics of the abstracted water volume (in mil. m³) in the DPBS RBD

Source: Annual Reports (2007-2017) on the Indices of water management. "Apele Moldovei" Agency

2.2. POINT SOURCE POLLUTION

Wastewater discharge:

In the DPBS RBD there are only 48 wastewater treatment plants, of which 39 are in operation. The total capacity of wastewater treatment plants is 126,0 thousand m³/day. The usability of treatment plants in the DPBS RBD is only 14%, which is conditioned both by economic and demographic decline of serviced cities and the very high level (over 40%) of wear and tear of the wastewater sewerage and treatment installations. Very poor technical conditions, superficial control of pollution sources, very low pollution payments and erratic fines generate an increased impact on water and the human health.

In the DPBS RBD there are 60 centralised wastewater discharge systems (fig. 7) and only 51 sewerage networks are in operation. 75% of sewerage networks have sewage treatment plants. The total length of sewerage networks is 750 km of which 701 km (93%) are functional. In 2017, the total volume of wastewater discharged was 7 million m³, of which: 1.85 million m³ from industry, 1.71 million m³ from agriculture and 3.44 million m³ from municipal waste.

Most urban settlements within the DPBS RBD are connected to sewage treatment plants (but to different extents). The average population connection to sewerage systems within the district is 11%, while population access to sewage treatment plants is only 4.7%. In most rural settlements the lack of treatment plants creates a potential source of pollution for aquifers.

Organic pollutants in the DPBS RBD from point source pollution in 2017 accounted for 2,316 tonnes of BOD and 3,937 tonnes of COD. The main sources of pollution with organic substances are municipal sewerage companies (domestic water supply) and the food industry (wine, milk and meat processing, etc.). The primary organic pollution is attributed to the main cities (agglomerations) within the district (Ungheni, Cahul, Hancesti, Edinet, Comrat), which together with the municipal wastewater remove about 65% of organic substances according to BOD₅ and 70% of organic substances according to COD.

In a very large number of cities, a high proportion of the population is still not connected to sewage systems, or the status of treatment plants is not in line with requirements. Among the districts featuring wastewater treatment plants, only the plant in Cantemir city meets all criteria.

Nutrient pollution, especially nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), can contribute to eutrophication of surface waters. It was calculated that 424.6 tonnes of N_{tot} and 77.2 tonnes of P_{tot} were discharged from all point sources during 2017. The main source of pollution was domestic sewage. The hazardous substances discharged during 2017 included: detergents - 0.08 t/year, oils and fats - 0.42 t/year.

The general tariff quota for sewerage services at the AMAC companies in DPBS RBD is 16.9 MDL/m³. The tariff quota for sewerage and wastewater treatment services provided to the population is 11.75 MDL/m³, for budgetary organisations – 29.47 MDL/m³ and economic agents – 28.70 MDL/m³.

2.3. DIFFUSE SOURCE POLLUTION

Cultivation of agricultural crops and use of fertilizers

Within the DPBS RBD, about 80% of land is used for agriculture, of which 57.7% is arable land, mostly used to grow cereal crops and technical plants; in the regions where irrigation is practised, vegetables are grown on these lands. According to the information obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics, 36,321 tons of mineral fertilizers were used for agricultural crops in the DPBS RBD in 2017. About 65 kilograms of mineral fertilizers were applied for one ha of arable land in that year. The quantity of the organic fertilizers used in 2017 was 5,931 t. The intensive use of chemical fertilizers contributes to the intensification of nitrification processes in aquatic basins.

Livestock production

The quantity and size of animal waste and manure are influenced by the size of animals, and it is stored in special cesspools for later use as organic fertilizers in agriculture, or washed away by rainwater, becoming a source of pollution.

Within the district, livestock productivity has dropped considerably due to the privatization and division of land into small plots, the disappearance of large livestock farms, poor food supply and low quality, the acute shortage of investment in the creation of new farms with high-performance technologies based on private ownership, and the increased price of energy resources.

The structure of livestock in 2017 was as follows: sheep and goats – 583,000 heads, pigs – 156,000 heads, cattle – 76,000 heads, horses – 15,000 heads.

Although animal population has fallen in recent years, its impact on the quality of water resources remains considerable.

To summarise the situation regarding nutrient inputs from the agricultural sector, emissions from diffuse sources (such as those from mineral and organic fertilizers and manure) are significant.

Solid Waste

Waste management raises very complex problems requiring coordinated action at all administration levels. By the end of 2017, within the DPBS RBD, the total volume of waste was generated was 729.4 thousand t. Existing hazardous waste represents 793.2 t. The storage of solid household waste as a result of the activity of individual farms and small businesses is widespread and represents an additional source of groundwater pollution. Only a few solid waste collection points are equipped with a full range of environmental protection tools. In most cases, the layer beneath the landfill is loessoid clay (clay), which accumulates and, in the long run, allows the penetration of pollutants into the first aquifer (alluvial deposits of the meadows and river terraces - a, adA₃). Currently, it is necessary to carry out further studies on the groundwater pollution generated by landfills.

2.4. HYDROMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES

The main types of hydromorphological alterations occurring within the DPBS RBD are the construction of reservoirs and ponds along the river courses, the regulation of rivers, the construction of flood protection dykes, etc.

The number of water accumulations (ponds and reservoirs) in the DPBS RBD within the Republic of Moldova is estimated at about 2,852. According to their origin, the anthropic ones predominate.

At present, within the DPBS RBD, the dyke system has a total length of about 365 km, of which about 51% is along the Prut River, and the rest on the rivers of Cogîlnic and Ialpug rivers.

Figure 7. Wastewater discharge – the main pressure within DPBS RBD

3. MONITORING

3.1. SURFACE WATER MONITORING

Historically, Moldovan SW quality monitoring started in the 1960s and was developed until the 1980s, with a focus on the transboundary rivers Dniester and Prut. The main objective of the monitoring programme is to provide information on the water quality of surface waters, identify cases of exceptional pollution and its sources, and notify the local and central authorities authorised to take mitigation and restoration measures.

Article 13 of the Moldovan Water Law states that systematic monitoring and recording of surface water status will be carried out by the central body in the field of environmental protection. The previous and current SW monitoring systems of Moldova have always had a clear focus on water quality, while other pressures such as hydro-morphological alterations have been considered only to a minor extent. However, long-term hydrological monitoring data are available for rivers. Currently Moldova is working on establishing a WFD-compliant monitoring network.

Until 2018, the State Hydrometeorological Service was the institution responsible for hydrobiological, hydrochemical and hydrological monitoring of surface waters. Since January 2019, the laboratories responsible for environmental monitoring have been transferred to the newly created Environmental Agency. In this reorganisational process, the on-going monitoring system has almost been put on hold.

3.1.1. Current surface water monitoring situation

According to the requirements of the WFD, the water quality monitoring in Moldova is divided into surveillance, operational and investigative monitoring.

Until 2013, the monitoring of **physico-chemical water quality** in surface waters of the DPBS RBD was carried out at 22 monitoring sites. In 2014 a new monitoring programme, which implemented key elements of the WFD, was started for the DPBS RBD. It included 52 monitoring stations on rivers (9 sites on the Prut River and 43 sites on tributaries of the Prut River or on surface waters of the DPBS RBD), and 6 standing waters (4 artificial lakes and 2 natural lakes). However, data are not available for all of these sites. Currently, 30 surveillance and 12 operational sites are situated on rivers, and 10 surveillance and 3 operational sites on lakes and reservoirs (fig. 8). The monitoring programme includes 25 general physico-chemical parameters (e.g. oxygen, nutrients) and 11 chemical parameters (e.g. heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons). In 2015, a large number of priority pollutants was also analysed.

Most of the physico-chemical water quality monitoring sites are also included in the **biological monitoring**. Monitoring includes analyses of phytobenthos, benthic invertebrates, phytoplankton and several other biological quality elements (BQE) not required under the WFD such as zooplankton and bacteria. There is no WFD-compliant classification method in use. Currently, the status assessment is based on existing boundaries for different biological quality elements, following the one-out-all-out principle. A major step towards WFD compliant biological monitoring was achieved during the EUWI+ project by development of an Ecological Status Classification System ESCS for macroinvertebrates. In lakes, the monitoring approach and programme are similar to those applied to rivers, but also include macrophytes as another BQE.

The current **hydrological monitoring** network (quantitative) within the DPBS RBD comprises 12 surface water quantity monitoring sites on rivers (3 on the Prut, the other 9 on other rivers). Until recently, hydro-morphological monitoring was restricted to hydrological parameters. Morphological parameters only started to be monitored during the EPIRB and EUWI+ projects (2013-2019).

3.1.2. Monitoring improvement

3.1.2.1. Chemical monitoring

The surveillance and operational monitoring sites will remain the same as in the current programme. However, it is recommended to revise and possibly adjust the number of sites. Additionally, investigative monitoring sites will be implemented if the need arises. Surveillance sites are planned to be monitored once per RBMP cycle, and operational sites twice (table 5). Depending on the depth of the lakes, 4-6 depth layers shall be investigated.

Most general physico-chemical parameters relevant under the EU WFD are monitored in the Republic of Moldova. Further parameters required to be monitored by the Water Framework Directive (general and priorities substances) shall be added to the programme. These include pesticides, dioxins, alkylphenols, organotin compounds, phthalates, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and volatile organic compounds (VOC). Considering the importance of the agricultural sector in the country, testing for pesticides needs to be included in surface water monitoring.

Table 5. Overview of proposed chemical monitoring in rivers and lakes
(reservoirs)

Monitoring	SWB	Quality Elements / Group of Parameters	Frequency:	
Chemical Surveillance Monitoring	Rivers (30 sites)	General Physico-Chemical Parameters	12x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		River Basin-Specific Pollutants		
		Priority Substances		
Chemical Operational Monitoring	Rivers (12 sites)	General Physico-Chemical Parameters	12x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any 2 years of the 6 years RBMP cycle
		River Basin-Specific Pollutants	-*	
		Priority Substances	-*	
Chemical Surveillance Monitoring	Lakes (10 sites)	General Physico-Chemical Parameters	6x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		River Basin-Specific Pollutants		
		Priority Substances		

Chemical Operational Monitoring	Lakes (3 sites)	General Physico-Chemical Parameters	6x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any 2 years of the 6 years RBMP cycle
		River Basin-Specific Pollutants	-*	
		Priority Substances	-*	

* If the risk assessment finds the SWB to be affected by point source or diffuse pollution, chemical analysis of the suspected substances should also be conducted. – Rivers: 12x; Lakes: 6x.

Figure 8. The network of surface water monitoring stations

3.1.2.2. Biological Monitoring

Surveillance and operational monitoring sites are the same as for chemical monitoring.

While currently several BQEs are monitored on all sites included in the monitoring programme, the limited resources will focus on phytoplankton, phytobenthos and macrozoobenthos during this RBMP cycle. Macrophytes and fish should be included in the next RBMP cycle (table 6).

In the operational monitoring, it is recommended to focus on those BQEs that are most sensitive to the dominant pressure – in case of significant point sources of organic pollution, or hydro-morphological alterations this is macrozoobenthos. In case of eutrophication (from diffuse or point sources), phytobenthos should be monitored in small rivers, and phytoplankton in medium to large rivers and lakes. In all cases, the development of a WFD-compliant classification system is required.

Table 6. Proposal for the biological monitoring in rivers and lakes (reservoirs) of in the DPBS RBD.

Monitoring	SWB	Quality Elements / Group of Parameters	Frequency:	
Biological Surveillance Monitoring	Rivers (30 sites)	Benthic Invertebrates	1x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		Phytobenthos (diatoms)		
Biological Operational Monitoring	Rivers (12 sites)	Benthic Invertebrates	1x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any 2 years of the 6 years RBMP cycle
		Phytobenthos (diatoms)		
Biological Surveillance Monitoring	Lakes (10 sites)	Phytoplankton	6x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
Biological Operational Monitoring	Lakes (3 sites)	Phytoplankton	6x within the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed within any 2 years of the 6 years RBMP cycle

3.1.2.3. Hydro-morphological monitoring

While a previous hydro-morphological description was carried out at single sites, the new monitoring shall cover the whole river network. A sampling campaign in 2019 was the starting point of hydro-morphological mapping in the whole DPBS river basin. During this RBMP cycle, the dataset needs to be increased through additional surveys.

The measuring of water levels at all lakes with surveillance monitoring sites needs to be included in the programme. The other hydrological monitoring sites remain as in the current monitoring.

3.1.3. Monitoring costs

The following estimations represent the costs of the full six years of an RBMP cycle. As mentioned in Table 5 and Table 6, the 40 surveillance sites will be investigated once per cycle (chemical monitoring 12x / year; biological monitoring of macrozoo- and phyto-benthos in rivers 1x / year, and of phytoplankton in medium/large rivers and lakes 6x / year), and the 15 operational monitoring sites will be sampled twice over the six-year period (same annual frequency).

Based on the survey costs for 2018 and 2019 in the EUWI+ project, the approximate costs of the surface water monitoring in the DPBS RBD can be estimated. Sampling and analyses of general physico-chemical parameters and all BQEs (benthic invertebrates, phyto-benthos, phytoplankton) for the proposed surveillance and operational monitoring sites will cost around € 104,000 in this RBMP cycle.

The cost estimation for the monitoring of priority pollutants is uncertain as these analyses are newly implemented in the national monitoring programme. Based on costs in other countries and assuming 15 parameters to be analysed on average, the rough cost estimate for priority pollutants is around € 245,000 to € 265,000. The actual costs will vary, depending on the number and kind of parameters analysed.

3.1.4. Monitoring results

3.1.4.1. Chemical status

The quality and chemical status of surface water bodies (SWB) was assessed on the basis of the monitoring results from 2013–2017 as well as annual surveys in the Prut river basin carried out during the EPIRB project. Based on physico-chemical parameters and specific substances, the water quality of the Prut River is affected throughout the entire course of the river, including the Costești-Stînca reservoir (“moderately polluted”). Most Prut tributaries are moderately to highly polluted, mainly due to organic pollution and oxygen deficits.

Based on the chemical data, the following monitoring sites are considered as being at risk of failing to meet the environmental objectives under Directive 2013/39/EU: Prut (Lipcani , Braniște village, Valea Mare village, Leova village, Giurgiulesti village); Draghiște, Fetești village; the Galmage Valley, Zarnești village; as well as the Costesti-Stînca reservoir.

3.1.4.2. Ecological status

According to the WFD, the assessment of the ecological status is primarily based on biological data. Supporting elements are physico-chemical, hydro-morphological parameters and specific pollutants.

A WFD compliant ecological status classification system (ESCS) for macroinvertebrates in rivers was introduced by EUWI+ (fig. 9).

Figure 9. Preliminary ecological classification of SWBs in the DPBS RBD

3.1.5. Programme of Measures related to surface water monitoring

During recent years within the EUWI+ project, significant improvement has been achieved in training and procurement of equipment, which is required for chemical, biological, and hydro-morphological monitoring. However, it is absolutely necessary to continue improving technical know-how and data through future surveys, additional parameters, and further BQEs in the national monitoring.

The construction of sewage treatment plants in urban and rural areas and the reduction of wastewater discharge by industry and diffuse pollution from agriculture should be priorities.

Considering the importance and prevalence of agriculture in the R. of Moldova, a sound and comprehensive management of this sector is indispensable to mitigate direct and indirect impacts on surface waters. In addition, water abstraction needs clear regulation and supervision.

3.2. GROUNDWATER MONITORING

The legal basis of the groundwater monitoring network is Government Decision Nr 932 of 20.11.2013, which specifies various elements that are fully in line with the requirements of the Water Framework Directive. The Agency for Geology and Mineral Resources (AGRM), which comes under the Ministry of Agriculture, Territory Development and Environment, manages routine national groundwater quantity and quality monitoring and the Moldavian Hydrogeological Expedition (EHGeoM) is in charge of monitoring and sampling.

During the Soviet era, the groundwater monitoring network in the Danube–Prut–Black–Sea–River Basin (DPBSRB) included about 340 wells. Today, the network consists of only 63 monitoring wells (fig. 10), which are all subject to quantitative and chemical monitoring.

In total 11 groundwater bodies have been identified and delineated in the DPBSRB, following the principles of the WFD. A review of the groundwater bodies (GWBs) and the groundwater monitoring network in the DPBSRB in 2018 showed that three of the eleven GWBs (MDDBSGWQ220, MDPRTGWQ230 and MDPRTGWQ510) lack a monitoring network and that 18 additional monitoring sites are therefore needed (6 sites per GWB) to cover all GWBs.

An assessment study in 2019 proposed to add 15 existing springs to the national groundwater monitoring network and to drill 3 new wells with an approximate depth of 15 m. The 3 new wells were drilled in Nov/Dec 2020 and all administrative requirements were fulfilled for including the 18 monitoring sites (15 springs and 3 new wells) into the national groundwater monitoring network. The equipment for continuous level monitoring, which is still needed, is estimated to cost in total about 100,000 MDL (€ 15,000) for all three wells.

Quantitative monitoring is done on a daily basis for all existing 63 wells in the flooding period and weekly in the period of stable groundwater levels. All sites are in operational condition or require only slight maintenance. This monitoring can now be extended with the additional 18 sites, incurring only minor additional costs. Currently, 15 monitoring sites are equipped with automatic sensors. EHGeoM is planning to refurbish 14 monitoring wells including the installation of automatic equipment which costs in total approximately 280,000 MDL (€ 14,000). It is planned to have at least two monitoring wells per GWB equipped with automatic sensors.

The groundwater chemical monitoring situation is relatively poor as it currently covers only 29 groundwater wells (seven of the eleven GWBs) and the monitoring frequency is irregular and insufficient. The minimum monitoring frequency of major ions is currently recommended twice per year but it actually varies from one to seven times per site within a 5-year period. Also the scope of analysed substances is not in accordance with legal requirements. Given that the list of hazardous substances in the Government Decision is too limited, several microelements and organic substances are not analysed.

Within the review of the chemical monitoring activity it was proposed to:

- ✓ Establish chemical groundwater monitoring at minimum 55 monitoring sites in the DPBSRB covering all GWBs (5 sites per GWB).
- ✓ Reduce the required monitoring frequency in such a way that the macro components and nutrients should be monitored once per year and the trace elements (metals) and hazardous substances (pesticides and organic substances) should be monitored every 3rd year. If a substance causes a risk, of course this substance also needs annual monitoring.
- ✓ Extend the legally required minimum list of chemical parameters for groundwater, in particular the list of hazardous substances, depending on new possible pollution factors from point and diffuse sources and the analytical capacity of the responsible institution(s).

Considering the proposed amendments (full coverage of the DPBSRB, amended monitoring frequency and additional parameters), the approximate costs for a six-year management plan period will result in: 6 x 71k MDL for macro components and nutrients, 2 x 183k MDL for trace elements and 2 x 265k MDL for hazardous substances which results in total in 1,322,000 MDL (€ 66,000) for the groundwater chemical monitoring over a period of six years (table 7).

Table 7. The total costs of groundwater monitoring programme for next cycle in the DPBS RBD

INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES	COSTS
Overview of one-time investment costs	
Automatic equipment for 3 new wells	100 000 MDL (5 000 €)
Automatic equipment for 14 existing and refurbished wells	280 000 MDL (14 000 €)
Total investment costs	480 000 MDL (24 000 €)
Overview of chemical monitoring costs for six years	
Total chemical monitoring (55 sites)	1,322,000 MDL (66 100 €)

Several GWBs are transboundary with Romania and Ukraine. It is very important to also establish monitoring sites for these transboundary GWBs. This requires mutual agreement on a monitoring programme featuring common standards for information exchange and joint assessment of GWB status.

The monitoring sites are unevenly distributed in the proposed GWBs (fig. 10).

Figure 10. The distribution of monitoring sites by delineated GWBs

3.3. IMPROVING THE MONITORING PROGRAM

This chapter includes the recommendations for a new monitoring network for surface water, in order to improve the monitoring system and to fill the gaps in the data sets.

3.3.1. Surface waters

3.3.1.1. Surveillance monitoring

Proposals regarding the frequency of monitoring by surveillance sections

According to the current RBMP for DBH DPMN, it is recommended to take samples for all chemical parameters 12 times during a year on rivers - once during a 6-year RBMP cycle. On lakes, the general physico-chemical parameters, river basin specific pollutants (RBSP) and priority substances shall be sampled 6 times during a year - once during a 6-year RBMP cycle (table 8).

Table 8. The recommended frequency of chemical monitoring at surveillance sections according to the first RBMP cycle of DBH DPMN

Monitoring	Water bodies	Quality elements / Groups of Parameters	Frequency:	
Chemical surveillance monitoring	Rivers	General physico-chemical parameters	12 times in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed in any of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		River basin specific pollutants		
		Priority substances		
	Lakes	General physico-chemical parameters	6 times in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	
		River basin specific pollutants		
		Priority substances		

Regarding biological quality elements (BQE), benthic and phytobenthic invertebrates shall be sampled in rivers once, during an RBMP cycle, and in lakes it is recommended to sample phytoplankton 6 times during a year, but once during an RBMP cycle (table 9).

Table 9. The recommended frequency of biological monitoring at surveillance sections according to the first RBMP cycle of DBH DPMN

Monitoring	Water bodies	Quality elements / Groups of Parameters	Frequency:	
Operational biological monitoring	Rivers	Benthic invertebrates	1 time in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed in any of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		Phytobenthos (diatomites)		
	Lakes	Phytoplankton	6 times in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	

3.3.1.2. Operational monitoring

Proposals regarding the frequency of monitoring at operational sections:

According to the current RBMP for DBH DPMN, it is recommended to sample all general physico-chemical parameters relevant 12 times during a year on rivers and 6 times during a year on lakes - twice during a 6-year RBMP cycle (table 10).

Regarding biological quality elements (BQE), benthic and phytobenthic invertebrates shall be sampled in rivers twice during an RBMP cycle, and in lakes, it is recommended to sample phytoplankton 6 times during a year - twice during an RBMP cycle (table 11). For point or diffuse sources of pollution, suspected priority substances and river basin-specific pollutants (RBSP) should also be sampled (rivers - 12 times and lakes - 6 times, twice during an RBMP cycle).

Table 10. The recommended frequency of chemical monitoring at operational sections according to the scheme of 2 times per RBMP cycle from DBH DPMN

Monitoring	Water bodies	Quality elements / Groups of Parameters	Frequency	
Operational chemical monitoring	Rivers	General physico-chemical parameters	12 times in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed in any 2 of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		River basin specific pollutants	-*	
		Priority substances	-*-	
	Lakes	General physico-chemical parameters	6 times in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	
		River basin specific pollutants	-*	
		Priority substances	-*	

* If during the risk assessment it is found that the water bodies are affected by point or diffuse sources of pollution, the chemical analysis of the suspected substances should be also carried out. – Rivers: 12x; Lakes: 6x.

Table 11. The recommended frequency of biological monitoring at operational sections according to the scheme of 2 times per RBMP cycle from DBH DPMN

Monitoring	Water bodies	Quality elements / Groups of Parameters	Frequency	
Operational biological monitoring	Rivers	Benthic invertebrates	1 time in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	To be executed in any 2 of the 6 years of the RBMP cycle
		Phytoplankton (diatoms)		
	Lakes	Phytoplankton	6 times in the selected year of the RBMP cycle	

4. RISK ASSESSMENT FOR SURFACE WATER BODY AND GROUNDWATER BODY STATUS

The pressure and impact analysis employed D.P.S.I.R. methodology (Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response - Anthropogenic Activity Pressure-State-Impact-Response). This required using information / data on anthropogenic activities and changes in the state of water resources as well as the monitoring data.

Assessing the impact of different types of significant pressures is intended to provide information to be used for risk analysis and water status characterization in accordance with Annex V of the WFD.

4.1. SURFACE WATER BODIES WITHIN DPBS RBD

The surface water are classified into natural and artificial. Among the natural surface water bodies, many heavily modified water bodies (HMWB) have been identified. The delimitation of surface water bodies and identification of heavily modified water bodies are based on several approaches.

Within the DPBS RBD, 128 surface water bodies were identified. A water body (Ialbug channel) has been identified as an artificial water body.

There are 92 heavily modified water bodies. The criteria for assigning them as heavily modified water bodies were:

- the presence of two or more accumulations of water along the river;
- presence of a regularised river segment (straightened);
- water quality (based on monitoring data).

The risk analysis was done according to the recommendations of the Guidance on the Hydro-Morphological and Physical-Chemical Approach for Pressure Impact Analysis (EPIRB project).

4.1.1. Risk assessment based on point source pollution impact

Water quality is influenced by the discharge of untreated or insufficiently treated wastewater from wastewater treatment plants into natural receptors. The largest volumes of untreated wastewater come from settlements that are supplied with water but not equipped with sewage systems and treatment plants. All SWBs featuring human agglomerations with a high level of connection to the sewerage system are at risk of not achieving the environmental objectives for good surface water quality. Of the 128 SWBs, 5 are “without any risk” to point pollution, 113 are “possibly at risk” and 10 are “at risk” (fig. 11).

4.1.2. Risk assessment based on diffuse source pollution impact

The highest source of diffuse pollution remains agriculture, which contributes to the pollution of surface and underground waters, including nutrients (N, P and K), pesticides and other plant protection products. In terms of land use, DPBS RBD is a typical agrarian region, where 125 SWBs (from all 128) have a share of agricultural land that exceeds 50% (at risk). Animal livestock has a major impact on the state of water resources in DPBS RBD. In addition to high nutrient emissions (over 12,000 tonnes of N and about 2,000 tons of P), livestock farming also indirectly contributes to water pollution. Applying the same “one-out-all-out” principle, 125 SWBs were judged to be “at risk” by the registered diffuse pollution (fig. 12).

Figure 11. Surface water bodies at risk for registered point source pollution

Figure 12. Surface water bodies at risk through the registered diffuse pollution

4.1.3. Risk assessment based on hydromorphological alterations

In the analysis of hydromorphological alterations, the following indicators were taken into account - **water abstraction, construction of reservoirs and ponds along the river, density of irrigation channels and regulation of the main river course.** According to the “one-out-all-out” principle, we obtain 37 SWBs with “not at risk”, 32 SWBs with a “possible risk” status and 59 SWBs with a “risk” status (fig. 13).

Figure 13. Surface water bodies at risk through the hydromorphological alterations

4.1.4. Overall pressure

Based on the “one-out-all-out” principle, all sub-basins within the DPBS RBD rank as “at risk” of not achieving the environmental objectives because one of the eight indicators used (diffuse pollution from agriculture) received the highest score (“at risk”) in 125 SWB for 128.

4.2. ASSESSMENT OF GROUNDWATER BODY RISK

All groundwater aquifers from DPBS RBD are delineated in eleven GWBs according to the existing hydrogeological model of the territory of Republic of Moldova. Identifying pressures on the use of groundwater and assessing risk constitute one of the most important objectives for effective groundwater management and monitoring. A process of data collection and analysis would aim to identify the type and magnitude of significant anthropogenic pressures to which groundwater is liable to be subject, including the following:

- Point sources and diffuse sources of pollution;
- Groundwater abstraction;
- Artificial recharge of groundwater;
- Land use patterns and practices.

Generally, the chemical composition of the groundwater is influenced by the lithological composition of the rocks, the depth of the horizon, the drainage characteristic of the horizon, large river valleys, and **anthropogenic / human factors (presence of towns and cities, etc)**. However, measuring the extent of an anthropogenic intrusion is complex, as some groundwater bodies have naturally elevated levels of salinity due to the aquifer geochemistry. Natural background concentrations of salinity indices are quite high because of the marine origin of water-bearing sediments, which still contain saline waters in their pores. In all cases, the fluctuations are close to natural, and at present, the impacts of the mentioned pressures are not significant (based on existing monitoring data). It should be noted that, at present, there are no complete monitoring data

to assess the condition of the groundwater bodies. However, the information available in the analysis indicate that the alluvial-deluvial (Holocene) and Pliocene-Pleistocene water bodies are at risk of failing to achieve good groundwater quantitative and good groundwater chemical status. Three groundwater bodies are probably at risk regarding groundwater quantity and quality. (table 12).

Table 12. Risk assessment for the groundwater bodies within the DPBS RBD

Nr. of horizon	Name of the aquifer or horizon	Index	GWB Code	Basin	Quantitative risk	Qualitative risk	Total risk	Level of confidence
1	Holocen alluvial-diluvial	aA3	MDDBS-GWQ120	Danube-Black Sea	R	R	R	Medium
2		aA3	MDPRT-GWQ130	Prut	R	R	R	Medium
3	Pliocene-Pleistocene	aA1+2 - aN22+3	MDDBS-GWQ220	Danube-Black Sea	R	R	R	Low
4		aA1+2 - aN22+3	MDPRT-GWQ230	Prut	R	R	R	Low
5	Pontian	N2p	MDDPB-GWD310	Danube-Prut-Black Sea	PR	PR	PR	Medium
6	Upper Sarmatian - Maeotian	N1s3-m	MDDPB-GWD420	Danube-Prut-Black Sea	PR	PR	PR	Medium
7	Middle Sarmatian, sandy and clay formations	N1s2 kd1-2	MDPRT-GWQ510	Prut	PR	PR	PR	Medium
8	Middle Sarmatian (Congerian)	N1s2	MDDPB-GWD620	Danube-Prut-Black Sea	N	N	N	Medium
9	Badenian-Sarmatian	N1b-s1-2	MDDPB-GWD730	Danube-Prut-Black Sea	N	N	N	Medium
10		N1b-s1	MDPRT-GWD740	Prut	N	N	N	Low
11	Cretaceous-Silurian	K2+S	MDPRT-GWD820	Prut	N	N	N	Low

5. IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING OF PROTECTED AREAS

The EU Water Framework Directive establishes that areas with special protection requirements stipulated by other European directives are identified as protected areas. These areas have their own objectives, standards and implementation measures, and some of them may require special protection and specific objectives in line with relevant European legislation, including the following directives:

- Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC;
- Drinking Water Directive 98/83/EC;
- Birds Directive 79/409/EEC;
- Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC;
- Nitrates Directive 91/676 / EEC on the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources;
- Urban Waste Water Directive 91/271 / EEC on Urban Waste Water Treatment;
- Bathing Water Directive 2006/7/EC

Article 6 of the EU Water Framework Directive requires Member States to establish a register of these protected areas, which must include the following categories:

- All bodies of water used for the abstraction of water intended for human consumption providing more than 10 m³ a day as an average or serving more than 50 persons, and those bodies of water intended for such future use (WFD Art 7(1))
- Protected areas of water abstractions for drinking purposes;
- Areas for the protection of economically important aquatic species;
- Protected areas for habitats and species where water is an important factor;
- Vulnerable zones to nitrates and nutrient sensitive areas;
- Bathing areas.

5.1. Protection areas for water abstraction for drinking purposes

In the Danube-Prut and Black Sea Hydrographic District there are 12 surface water abstraction points (according to the data provided by the National Public Health Centre), of which 6 points have so far been identified and mapped - all located on the Prut River. According to the data provided by the National Centre for Public Health and the Agency for Geology and Mineral Resources, there are 137 water wells in the Danube-Prut and Black Sea Hydrographic District, of which 26 have a monitoring purpose (fig. 14).

5.2. Areas for the protection of economically important aquatic species

Within DPBS RBD, economically valuable fish species have been identified on the Costești- Stînca reservoir and the Lower Prut River (from the town of Cahul) (fig. 15).

5.3. Protected areas for habitats and species where water is an important factor

Areas of avifauna importance within DPBS RBD have been identified on the basis of habitats (sites) where the species of birds found in Annex I of the Birds Directive present on this site have been included. Species listed in Annex I are the subject of special conservation measures for their habitats to ensure their survival and reproduction in the area of distribution.

Following the field inventory, three sites along the Prut River, which require such status (fig. 16), were identified:

1. Costesti Reservoir – **7 species** according to Annex I of the Birds Directive;
2. The Scientific Reserve “Padurea Domneasca” – **22 species**;
3. The Lower Prut (complex of natural lakes Manta and Beleu) – **23 species**.

Figure 14. Drinking water abstraction points

Figure 15. Areas with economically valuable fish species

Figure 16. Areas of avifauna importance

5.4. Sensitive and vulnerable areas of nutrients

Sensitive areas are those surface waters where it is possible to prove the impact of urban wastewater on the increased nitrates loading in surface water bodies. Due to the fact that most localities do not have wastewater treatment plants that meet EU requirements, it is preferable to declare the entire DPBS RBD as a nutrient-sensitive area. This option is basically the result of the provisions of Article 5 (8) of the European Directive 91/271/EEC on urban waste water treatment and assumes that the requirements for the intensified nitrogen and phosphorus disposal will refer to all agglomerations of more than 10,0 thousand P.E. (Population Equivalent) (fig. 17).

Figure 17. Areas proposed for designation as nutrient-sensitive areas

The designation of ***nitrate-vulnerable zones*** was based on monitoring data of surface water quality (for the period 2012-2018), provided by the Environment Agency, and data regarding the monitoring of groundwater (for the period 2006-2016), provided by the Agency of Geology and Mineral Resources. According to the data analysis results, no exceedance of NO_3 concentration is present in the surface waters, and in the groundwater aquifers, essential exceedances (about 41% of the country territory) are recorded in the case of the Holocene alluvial-deluvial aquifer (phreatic) (fig. 18).

Figure 18. Amount of nitrates (NO_3) recorded, mg/l

5.5. Bathing areas

Bathing areas are designated where bathing is regulated by the National Agency for Public Health (NAPH), based on the quality of water resources, the infrastructure and services provided, and other measures taken to encourage bathing, including promotional measures for touristic bathing areas. Within the DPBS RBD only one area meets the requirements for bathing areas - the Costesti-Stinca reservoir (fig. 19).

Figure 19. The Costesti-Stinca reservoir

6. ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTIVES

The Water Framework Directive establishes in art. 4 (section 1) the environmental objectives, including essentially the following elements:

- **for surface water bodies: achieving good ecological condition and good chemical condition, respectively good ecological potential and good chemical condition for the heavily modified and artificial water bodies;**
- **for groundwater bodies: achieving good chemical condition and good quantitative condition;**
- **progressive reduction of pollution with priority substances and gradual cessation or elimination of emissions, discharges and losses of priority dangerous substances** into the surface waters by implementing the necessary measures;
- “preventing or limiting” the discharge of pollutants into the groundwater by implementing measures;
- **reversing the trends** of significant and sustainable growth of pollutant concentrations in groundwater;
- non-deterioration of the condition of the surface waters and groundwater (Art. 4.1 (a) (i), Art. 4.1 (b) (i) of the WFD);
- **for protected areas: achieving the objectives set by the specific legislation.**

6.1. Environmental objectives for surface waters

For the surface water bodies within the DPBS RBD, the related environmental objectives have been established, depending on the category of the surface water body, for respectively: natural water bodies (rivers, lakes), heavily modified water bodies (rivers, accumulation lakes, heavily modified natural lakes) and artificial water bodies.

Based on the fact that out of the 128 surface water bodies 125 are at risk of not meeting the environmental objective, for the management cycle of 2022-2027 a derogation will be required from achieving the environmental objectives for most water bodies. Another reason to insist on exceptions is the total lack for funding for the programme of measures provided for in the current management cycle (2017-2022).

- Thus, regarding the environmental objectives, the following can be mentioned:
- by applying the provisions of the art. 4.4, the objectives of “good status” (ecological and chemical/ good ecological potential and good chemical status) will be achieved in the planning cycle of 2022-2027 by 37 surface water bodies (figure 20);
- the water bodies that shall need more time and deeper knowledge on the status and the degradation causes.

The **objective of “non-deterioration of condition”** of water bodies is one of the key elements regarding the protection of water bodies.

Figure 20. Environmental objectives for surface water bodies for 2022-2027

6.2. Environmental objectives for groundwater

The environmental objectives for the condition of groundwater bodies (tab. 13) involve the attainment of a good quantitative condition and good (chemical) qualitative condition, and the guarantee of the non-deterioration thereof. The environmental objectives represented by “good condition” from the qualitative point of view are defined by the threshold values established at the level of groundwater bodies in the Republic of Moldova and which have been approved by the GD No. 931 of 20/11/2013 for the approval of the regulation regarding the groundwater quality requirements.

For the groundwater bodies within the DPBS RBD, the environmental objectives established can be found in table 13.

Table 13. Environmental objectives for groundwater bodies within the DPBS RBD

Nr. of horizon	Name of the aquifer or horizon	Index	Code	Environmental objectives
1	Holocen alluvial-diluvial	aA3	MDDBSGWQ120	prevention or limitation the input of pollutants
2		aA3	MDPRTGWQ130	prevention or limitation the input of pollutants
3	Pliocene-Pleistocene	aA1+2-aN22+3	MDDBSGWQ220	prevention or limitation the input of pollutants
4		aA1+2-aN22+3	MDPRTGWQ230	prevention or limitation the input of pollutants
5	Pontian	N2p	MDDPBGWD310	protection, improvement and restoration
6	Upper Sarmatian - Maeotian	N1s3-m	MDDPBGWD420	ensure a balance between abstraction and recharge
7	Middle Sarmatian, sandy and clay formations	N1s2 kd1-2	MDPRTGWQ510	protection, improvement and restoration
8	Middle Sarmatian (Congerian)	N1s2	MDDPBGWD620	ensure a balance between abstraction and recharge
9	Badenian-Sarmatian	N1b-s1-2	MDDPBGWD730	ensure a balance between abstraction and recharge
10		N1b-s1	MDPRTGWD740	ensure a balance between abstraction and recharge
11	Cretaceous-Silurian	K2+S	MDPRTGWD820	ensure a balance between abstraction and recharge

6.3. Environmental objectives for protected areas

In the context of art. 4.1 of the Water Framework Directive, the objectives for the protected areas involve ensuring compliance with all of the standards and objectives provided in the legislation in the field, thus:

- Protection of the quality of water used for drinking purposes and reducing the level of treatment required for the production of drinking water by establishing specific norms/ standards for the quality parameters/ indicators – areas designated for abstracting waters to be used for drinking purposes.
- Protection and improvement of the quality of those fresh waters that maintain or could maintain ichthyofauna – areas designated for the protection of economically important aquatic species.
- Conservation of natural habitats, species of flora and fauna, which are found under pristine conditions on the national territory and are related to water bodies. Taking into account the specific objectives for the protection of species and water-dependent habitats – areas designated for the protection of habitats or species where maintaining or improving the water status is an important factor for the protection thereof, including the sites for Nature 2000.
- Reducing water pollution caused by the nitrates from agricultural sources, preventing nitrate pollution, rationalizing and optimizing the use of chemical and organic fertilizers containing nitrogen compounds – areas vulnerable to nitrates. The action program will be applied to the designated areas and will include the measures provided for in the Code of Good Agricultural Practices.
- Protection of the environment from damage due to the discharge of urban waste waters – areas sensitive to nutrients. The action programme will be applied to the designated areas and will include in particular actions to improve the wastewater treatment system.
- Preserving, protecting and improving the quality of the environment, as well as protecting the health of people, through a proper management of the quality of bathing waters – water bodies designated as recreational waters, including areas designated as bathing waters.

7. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF WATER USE

Water supply in the DPBS RBD is largely ensured by non-centralised water sources, which are not covered by current records and metering. According to State Environmental Inspectorate data, 74.3 thousand wells were identified in the perimeter of DPBS RBD (table 14). Overall, 84% of the wells are functional and can be used in households. In addition, 983 springs are used for water supply, of which 72% are functional.

Table 14. The number and status of wells and springs from districts of DPBS RBD

Districts	Wells			Springs		
	total	arranged	%	total	arranged	%
Ocnita	4159	3936	95	43	43	100
Briceni	14587	14038	96	56	39	70
Edinet	15412	15412	100	97	85	88
Rascani	3681	3586	97	95	42	44
Glodeni	4927	3941	80	155	103	66
Falesti	4189	3815	91	30	19	63
Ungheni	5028	4897	97	101	54	53
Nisporeni	1571	1230	78	138	138	100
Hancesti	4232	3628	86	79	62	78
Cimislia	2915	662	23	5	5	100
Basarabasca	680	360	53	5	3	60
Cantemir	1574	78	5	55	10	18
Leova	3975	2937	74	14	14	100
Cahul	1592	95	6	42	42	100
Taraclia	194	165	85	26	21	81
UTA Gagauzia	3167	1662	52	27	19	70
Causeni	1280	633	49	6	4	67
Stefan-Voda	1117	1050	94	9	8	89
DPBS RBD	74280	62125	84	983	711	72
Total RM	178134	145097	81	3042	1990	65

The average tariff for water supply services in the DPBS RBD over a decade is 14.6 MDL/m³, but was 17.2 MDL (€ 0.87)/m³ in 2018, which exceeds the general average of AMAC companies in the country at 1.5 MDL/m³ (table 15). The increase in the general tariff for water supply services is, on average, 71%, (from 10.1 MDL/m³ in 2007 to 17.2 MDL/m³ in 2018), and 43 % in the Euro equivalent¹.

Table 15. The average tariffs for public water supply services of AMAC companies in DPBS RBD, in MDL/m³ (without VAT)

Nr.	Towns	Years												Increase, %
		2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	
1	Ocnita	9,5	9,5	9,5	14,2	15,5	19,2	19,2	19,2	19,2	19,2	19,2	19,2	202
2	Briceni	12,5	12,5	12,5	12,8	12,8	12,8	12,8	12,8	12,8	12,8	12,8	12,8	103
3	Edinet	9,1	13,5	21,4	21,4	21,4	21,4	21,4	21,4	21,4	21,4	24,3	24,3	266
4	Glodeni	14,6	14,6	14,6	19,5	23,6	23,6	23,6	23,6	23,6	23,6	23,6	23,6	162
5	Falesti	10,2	10,2	10,2	10,2	12,4	12,4	14,5	14,5	14,5	14,5	14,5	14,5	142
6	Ungheni	4,0	6,2	6,2	6,2	7,7	7,7	9,0	9,0	9,0	9,0	15,0	15,0	374
7	Nisporeni	10,8	10,8	15,1	15,1	21,9	13,7	16,9	16,9	16,9	16,9	16,9	16,9	156
8	Hîncești	8,3	9,0	9,0	9,0	14,0	22,4	22,1	22,1	22,1	22,1	22,1	22,1	265
9	Cimisia			8,0	8,0	10,0	10,0	14,1	14,1	14,1	14,1	17,0	17,0	213
10	Basara-beasca	6,5	6,5	9,4	9,4	9,4	9,7	9,7	9,7	9,7	9,7	9,7	9,7	149
11	Leova	6,3	8,3	8,3	8,3	13,7	13,7	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	334
12	Cantemir	8,8	8,8	13,3	13,3	14,1	14,1	14,1	14,1	14,1	14,1	14,1	14,1	160
13	Cahul	9,0	9,0	11,3	11,3	11,3	11,3	11,3	11,3	11,3	11,3	13,9	13,9	155
14	Taraclia	15,7	15,7	15,7	16,5	13,6	13,6	13,6	13,6	13,6	13,6	15,0	15,0	95
15	Comrat	7,5	7,5	12,3	12,3	14,2	14,2	19,0	19,0	19,0	19,0	19,0	19,0	255
16	Ceadr Lunga	14,1	14,1	12,5	12,5	15,8	18,9	18,9	18,9	18,9	18,9	18,9	18,9	134
17	Vulcanesti	8,5	8,5	10,8	10,8	15,5	15,5	15,5	15,5	15,5	15,5	15,5	15,5	183
18	Stefan Voda	15,4	15,4	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	17,6	114
	DPBS RBD	10,1	10,6	12,1	12,7	14,7	15,1	16,3	16,3	16,3	16,3	17,2	17,2	171
	Total AMAC	9,4	10,0	11,3	12,2	13,6	14,0	14,8	14,9	15,0	15,3	15,7	15,7	167

<?> Official average exchange rate from 2007-2018 was 17.89 MDL/€1, and in 2018 - 19.85 MDL/€1

Unlike water supply tariffs, the tariffs for wastewater evacuation and purification do not only reflect the costs related to the operation of these systems but also a significant part of the ecological costs. Therefore, the tariff for sewerage and treatment services must necessarily include environmental damage or loss of ecosystem services by wastewater discharges into rivers. In addition, both tariffs constitute the “price of water”. The average tariff for sewerage services at AMAC companies in DPBS RBD is, on average, 14,0 MDL(€ 0.85)/m³ or with ≈2.0 MDL/m³ higher than the average national tariff (table 16).

Table 16. The dynamics of average tariff of public sewerage services for AMAC enterprises from DPBS HD, in MDL/m³ (without VAT)

No.	Towns	Years												Increase, %
		2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	
1	Ocnita	7,0	7,0	7,0	12,4	14,3	18,1	18,1	18,1	18,1	18,1	18,1	18,1	259
2	Briceni	11,1	11,1	11,1	14,3	14,3	14,3	14,3	14,3	14,3	14,3	14,3	14,3	129
3	Edinet	7,2	7,2	17,6	17,9	17,9	17,9	17,9	17,9	17,9	17,9	27,0	27,0	373
4	Glodeni	21,1	21,1	21,1	22,6	25,0	25,0	25,0	25,0	25,0	25,0	25,0	25,0	118
5	Falesti	10,6	10,6	10,6	10,6	13,4	13,4	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	158
6	Ungheni	5,7	5,7	5,7	5,7	7,5	7,5	8,6	8,6	8,6	8,6	9,4	9,4	164
7	Nisporeni	7,4	7,4	12,0	12,0	10,0	9,1	19,7	19,7	19,7	19,7	19,7	19,7	265
8	Hîncești	7,6	8,4	8,4	8,4	13,9	16,5	13,6	13,6	13,6	13,6	13,6	13,6	179
9	Cimislia			8,4	8,4	8,4	8,4	8,4	8,4	8,4	8,4	17,2	17,2	205
10	Basara-beasca	7,5	7,5	8,8	8,8	8,8	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	11,5	153
11	Leova	7,1	7,4	7,4	7,4	16,6	16,6	21,2	21,2	21,2	21,2	21,2	21,2	299
12	Cantemir	4,8	4,8	7,0	7,0	6,5	6,5	6,5	6,5	6,5	6,5	6,5	6,5	135
13	Cahul	3,7	3,7	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,6	9,2	9,2	250
14	Taraclia	18,3	18,3	18,3	26,5	19,5	19,5	20,0	20,0	20,0	20,0	16,0	16,0	87
15	Comrat	7,5	7,5	16,7	16,7	19,3	19,3	26,8	26,8	26,8	26,8	26,8	26,8	357
16	Ceadr Lunga	14,4	14,4	14,5	14,5	18,3	21,3	21,3	21,3	21,3	21,3	21,3	21,3	147
17	Vulcanesti	9,9	9,9	11,8	11,8	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	16,7	168
18	Stefan Voda	10,9	10,9	13,9	13,9	13,7	13,7	13,7	13,7	13,7	13,7	13,7	13,7	125
	DPBS RBD	9,5	9,6	11,4	12,4	13,8	14,4	15,8	15,8	15,8	15,8	16,9	16,9	177
	Total AMAC	8,7	9,0	10,3	11,0	11,9	12,4	13,6	13,5	13,5	13,9	14,0	14,0	160

The “Moldova Apa-Canal” Association companies in DPBS RBD are characterised by low profitability, both in water supply and sewerage and wastewater treatment services (table 17). Overall, the costs for water supply services exceeded the tariffs at 4.6 MDL (€0.23)/m³ and the cost recovery rate from these tariffs is on average 79%. Despite the considerable increase (+71%) in tariffs, at all AMAC companies in DPBS RBD, except those in Ungheni, the costs considerably exceed the tariffs for water supply services. Moreover, in almost all towns in the study region these negative differences increased in recent years.

Table 17. The ratio between the tariff and the cost of water and sewerage services in DPBS RBD, in MDL/ m³ (2017)

	Localities	Water supply					Sewerage and treatment					Total				
		Tariff	Cost	Difference			Tariff	Cost	Difference			Tariff	Cost	Difference		
				MDL	€	% ²			MDL	€	%			MDL	€	%
1	Ocnita	18,4	26,2	-7,8	-0,39	70	17,1	22,1	-5	-0,25	77	35,5	48,3	-12,8	-0,64	73
2	Briceni	13,8	16,2	-2,4	-0,12	85	15,1	17,6	-2,5	-0,13	86	28,9	33,8	-4,9	-0,25	86
3	Edinet	23,7	27,1	-3,4	-0,17	87	28,6	20,1	8,5	0,43	142	52,3	47,2	5,1	0,26	111
4	Glodeni	18,9	22,3	-3,4	-0,17	85	22,6	28,7	-6,1	-0,31	79	41,5	51	-9,5	-0,48	81
5	Falesti	13,7	16,6	-2,9	-0,15	83	14,5	14,8	-0,3	-0,02	98	28,2	31,4	-3,2	-0,16	90
6	Ungheni	12,7	12,1	0,6	0,03	105	9,6	9,8	-0,2	-0,01	98	22,3	21,9	0,4	0,02	102
7	Nisporeni	18,1	19,6	-1,5	-0,08	92	18,1	20,6	-2,5	-0,13	88	36,2	40,2	-4,0	-0,20	90
8	Hîncești	23,5	28,5	-5	-0,25	82	14,4	15,6	-1,2	-0,06	92	37,9	44,1	-6,2	-0,31	86
9	Cimislia	13,7	17,5	-3,8	-0,19	78	8,4	4,8	3,6	0,18	175	22,1	22,3	-0,2	-0,01	99
10	Basarabasca	12,4	18,4	-6	-0,30	67	16,2	16,7	-0,5	-0,03	97	28,6	35,1	-6,5	-0,33	81
11	Leova	18,5	24,4	-5,9	-0,30	76	14,2	22	-7,8	-0,39	65	32,7	46,4	-13,7	-0,69	70
12	Cantemir	12,5	17,4	-4,9	-0,25	72	6,4	6,4	0	0	100	18,9	23,8	-4,9	-0,25	79
13	Cahul	13,8	15,4	-1,6	-0,08	90	9,8	10,9	-1,1	-0,06	90	23,6	26,3	-2,7	-0,14	90
14	Taraclia	15,9	17,1	-1,2	-0,06	93	17,3	19,1	-1,8	-0,09	91	33,2	36,2	-3	-0,15	92
15	Comrat	17,5	28,8	-11,3	-0,57	61	21,2	15,1	6,1	0,31	140	38,7	43,9	-5,2	-0,26	88
16	Ceafâr-Lunga	18,5	27,7	-9,2	-0,46	67	17,2	28,3	-11,1	-0,56	61	35,7	56	-20,3	-1,02	64
17	Vulcănești	19,2	25,3	-6,1	-0,31	76	22,2	23,3	-1,1	-0,06	95	41,4	48,6	-7,2	-0,36	85
18	Stefan-Voda	18,4	25,4	-7	-0,35	72	14,1	18,1	-4	-0,20	78	32,5	43,5	-11	-0,55	75
	DPBS RBD	16,8	21,4	-4,6	-0,23	79	15,9	17,4	-1,5	-0,08	91	32,8	38,9	-6,1	-0,31	84
	AMAC	10,8	11,4	-0,6	-0,03	95	5,4	5,8	-0,4	-0,02	93	16,2	18,5	-2,3	-0,12	88

8. PROGRAMME OF MEASURES

PoMs serve the key purpose of reaching EU WFD objectives, in particular good water status, and hence of providing regulatory actions to reach, maintain and/or improve water status. Moreover, PoMs should be designed to reduce catchment pressures in order to improve ecosystem services rather than element classification.

In order to achieve the objectives, WFD Article 11 sets out two types of measures:

- Basic measures
- Supplementary measures

Basic measures are obligatory and they are the minimum requirements to be included in the PoM. Their aim is to meet the requirements of other EU Directives which are related to WFD implementation, for example, measures associated with the implementation of other Community legislation for the protection of waters (WFD Article 11(3)a and Annex VI, e.g. measures to achieve compliance with the objectives of the Nitrates and Urban Waste Water Treatment Directives, etc.

Supplementary measures are designed and implemented in addition to the basic measures where they are necessary to achieve the environmental objectives of WFD in accordance with Article 4. Supplementary measures would include additional legislative powers, fiscal measures, research, educational campaigns that go beyond the basic measures and are necessary for the achievement of objectives.

It is important to mention that all measures (basic and supplementary) are determined in the next WFD planning cycle and that there is a need to check whether they:

- are technically feasible;
- ensure the achievement of good status in time and in combination with the basic measures;
- are disproportionately expensive to achieve the environmental objectives.

8.1. BASIC MEASURES

Basic measures are an obligatory part of PoMs and, therefore, include the legally binding implementation of EU Directives other than the EU WFD to achieve *good water status*. These other EU Directives and their implementation foresee measures relating e.g. to water protection to reduce the discharge of nitrates and hazardous substances or any discharge limitation from point sources of pollution as well as water protection for water supply purposes. The other EU Directives that foster the implementation of basic measures have been transposed into the national legislation of the EU Member States and are summarised in Table 14.

Table 18. EU Directives relevant to be addressed through basic measures in PoMs

Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (91/271/EEC)
Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC)
Drinking Water Directive (98/83/EC)
Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC)
Bathing Water Directive (2006/7/EC)
Sewage Sludge Directive (86/278/EEC)
Major Accidents Directive (96/82/EC)
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (85/337/EEC)
Birds Directive (79/409/EEC)
Industrial Emission Directive (2010/75/EU)
Plant Production Products Directive (91/414/EEC)

In addition to the measures listed above, EU WFD Article 11(3) requires basic measures in addition to those relating to the implementation of other EU Directives. These other basic measures prevent any negative impacts on water status and are listed and described in Table 15.

Table 19. Other basic measures relevant to be addressed in PoMs

Measures to apply the principle of recovery of costs for water use (WFD Article 9)
Measures to promote efficient and sustainable water u
Measures to protect drinking water sources
Measures to control abstraction and impoundment of surface and ground waters
Measures to control point and diffuse pollution source
Measures to prohibition direct discharge into groundwater
Measures to manage priority substances
Measures to control physical modifications of surface water
Measures that control any other actions that can impact on water status
Measures to prevent accidental pollution

8.2. SUPPLEMENTARY MEASURES

Supplementary measures are optional and have to be established and implemented in case basic measures cannot ensure the achievement of the environmental objectives and “good water status”. Supplementary measures are mainly related to the water body at local level, while basic measures are linked to the national and basin-wide levels.

The EU WFD provides a list of supplementary measures (in an annex) listing the implementation of, for example, agreements and regulation codes of practice, economic instruments, etc. Since supplementary measures complement basic measures, they should be proportionate in costs, transparent and pragmatic.

8.3. SELECTED MEASURES

Based on all types of pressures present in the DPBS RBD, a set of measures has been selected to address the main problems identified in the field of water resource management. For point source pollution related to the discharge of urban waste water, 11 measures (8 basic measures and 3 additional measures) have been selected (tab. 16 and fig. 21).

Table 20. Selected measures for point source pollution

Type of measure			
No.	Basic measures	No.	Supplementary measures
1.	Develop master plan for WSS and improve governance for WSS including municipality association development for larger project management capacities	1.	Construction (extension) and modernisation of the storm water sewerage system
2.	Construction of wastewater treatment plants	2.	Control of wastewater in terms of its impact on the environment (for example, low phosphorus detergents or removal of phosphates from detergents)
3.	Modernisation of treatment technologies in existing treatment plants	3.	Introduction of an efficient tax system for wastewater collection and treatment financing
4.	Construction of individual wastewater treatment systems for areas with low population density		
5.	Construction (extension) and modernisation of sewage systems		
6.	Control of industrial pollution sources (reducing pollution at source reduces the costs associated with treatment and produces environmental benefits)		
7.	Inventory action and more rigorous control by the Environmental Inspectorate of the sources of wastewater discharge in rivers		
8.	Implementation of the water resources monitoring programme		

For the diffuse pollution sources, 8 measures (6 basic and 2 additional measures) have been selected, shown in table 17.

Table 21. Selected measures for diffuse source pollution

Type of measure			
No.	Basic measures	No.	Supplementary measures
1.	Implementation of the code of good agricultural practices for water protection against nitrate pollution from agricultural sources (regulating the use of fertilizers in agriculture, awareness rising and control development)	1.	Promotion by non-governmental organisations of the code of good agricultural practices to reduce pollution
2.	Delimitation of the riparian protection strips (according to the provisions of Law No. 440-XIII of 27.04.1995) and plant protection strips	2.	Organisation of trainings on sustainable livestock breeding
3.	Elaboration of rules / standards regarding optimal livestock size in relation to a certain area of pasture (in accordance with the EU Nitrates Directive (91/676 / CEE))		
4.	Implementation of the Action Plan for Nitrate Vulnerable Areas (for Nitrate Vulnerable Areas delimited in accordance with the EU Nitrate Directive (91/676 / CEE))		
5.	Avoidance of grazing within the riparian water protection strips		
6.	Implementation of the programme for monitoring water resources (Environmental Agency) and controls carried out by the Environmental Inspectorate		

For the improved governance and stewardship of the basin, 10 measures (6 basic and 4 additional measures) have been selected, shown in table 18.

Table 22. Measures selected for environmental stewardship of the basin

Type of measures			
No.	Basic measures	No.	Supplementary measures
1.	Improvement of the system for monitoring the water resources in quality and quantity;	1.	Training of farmers on efficient use and storage of water resources;
2.	Configuration of the sanitary protection area to protect the drinking water sources quality;	2.	Promotion of the efficient and sustainable use of water;
3.	Regulations for catchments and arrangements to prevent the deterioration of the condition (status) of the water body (the control system of the licenses for water use);	3.	Advertising campaigns that promote the efficient use of water by individual households;
4.	Development of the regulation (rules) for the efficient use of water	4.	Review of the payment system for water use, to recover all costs.
5.	Develop digitalization efforts to increase environmental data availability and sharing		
6.	Control (monitoring, counting) of the volume of water that may be abstracted or discharges (licenses, permits).		

For hydromorphological pressures (alterations), 11 measures (8 basic and 3 additional measures) have been selected as shown in table 19.

Table 23. Selected measures for improved ecosystems

Type of measures			
No.	Basic measures	No.	Supplementary measures
1.	Establishment of ecological flow in rivers (e.g. controlled discharge from lakes and ponds of the flow required for optimum ecological conditions downstream)	1.	Development of technical regulations for the exploitation of aquatic basins
2.	Creation of optimal conditions for ensuring continuity of the watercourse, especially for sediment transport (management)	2.	Elaboration of a technical guide / normative act regarding the management of clogged lakes / ponds
3.	Improved continuity of sediment transportation through the proper management of the dams	3.	Strengthening of the hydrological monitoring system
4.	Removal of alluviums and regulation of sediment extraction		
5.	Clearance of clogged ponds / lakes		

6.	Improved status of aquatic and riparian habitats (re-naturalisation)		
7.	Support of hydraulic engineering measures for morphological restoration of the water-course		
8.	Strengthening of the activity of the Environmental Inspectorate regarding the inspection of water bodies		

To reduce the pressures caused by climate change, 11 measures (6 basic and 5 additional measures) have been selected, shown in table 21 and figure 24.

Table 24. Measures selected to reduce pressures caused by climate change

Type of measures			
No.	Basic measures	No.	Supplementary measures
1.	Updating of normative acts in the field of flood	1.	Provision of institutional support through technical assistance
2.	Develop territorial flood risk management and water balance restoration plans in priority areas	2.	Research to evaluate the current and possible effects of climate change on water bodies
3.	Restoration of flood areas and wetlands	3.	Competitive financing of target programmes in research institutes to study the impact of climate change on different ecosystems and economic sectors
4.	Improvement of the status of protection dams	4.	Promotion of adaptive agriculture
5.	Implementation of an early warning system	5.	Afforestation (reforestation)
6.	Use of efficient irrigation technologies to save water;		

Figure 21. Basic measures proposed for urban wastewater discharges

Figure 22. Basic measures proposed for hydromorphological alterations

Figure 23. Basic measures proposed to reduce flood risk

Figure 24. Basic measures proposed for adaptation to climate change

Thus, the total (preliminary) list of measures selected comprises 52 actions (37 basic and 15 additional). However, not all measures will be selected for the next implementation cycle due to lack of funding and appropriate agreements. The final list of measures will be established as a result of the economic analysis of the programme of measures.

The total cost of the measures selected for implementation is estimated at about 3.2 billion lei (or 161 million EURO) (fig. 25).

The measures selected will be analysed in terms of policies, rights and financial taxes used for implementation, and their distribution by sector, regardless of whether they are basic or supplementary and when they are planned to become operational.

Figure 25. Cost Estimate for the Implementing Proposed Measures (million MDL / %)

9. MAIN ISSUES

During the development of RBMP for DPBS RBD, a number of problems of different natures were identified that lead to deficiency in water resources and a deterioration in their quality. The main issues identified are presented below:

9.1. HEALTH: ESTABLISH SAFE DRINKING WATER

- Only 11% of the population in DPBS RBD has access to centralised systems for discharged and wastewater treatment. Expansion of the sewerage network should be a priority in the coming years.
- Around half of the DPBS RBD population has access to a centralised water supply system. However, a large part of the population, especially from rural areas, has no access to a qualitative water supply. This issue will remain a priority for the next cycle of the RBMP.
- The quality of the water supply in schools and in institutions for children is inadequate (54.4% of the samples exceed the maximum admissible concentrations for the sanitary-chemical parameters and 20.2% of the samples exceed the maximum admissible concentrations of the microbiological parameters). This situation requires additional measures to improve the drinking water pre-treatment system.
- The occurrence of dysentery is significantly lower in the south part of the basin where the access to controlled drinking water is higher. Thus, underground waters should be used more intensely by the population, provided that they are demineralised first.
- Standardisation should be established for water use, especially for household needs; some records indicate overconsumption without application of the differentiated tariff.

9.2. WATER RESOURCES QUALITY: reduce pollution

- The largest volumes of untreated wastewaters come from settlements that are supplied with water, but do not have sewage systems and treatment plants. In the DPBS RBD there are only 48 wastewater treatment plants, of which 39 are in operation. The number of sewage treatment plants, especially in human agglomerations, needs to be expanded and existing ones need to be modernised.
- Of the 19 urban localities, only 2 cities (Leova and Cimislia) have wastewater treatment plants that conform to the requirements of Directive 91/271 / EEC. Three cities (Briceni, Glodeni and Tvardita) require building a new treatment plant, while the treatment plants in the other cities require modernisation.
- Agriculture is the main source of water pollution. The implementation of the Code of Good Agricultural Practice, as well as the delineation of riverside wooded strips, would reduce the pollution from this source.
- Improving the monitoring programme could increase the quality of water resources by identifying the sources of pollution earlier.

9.3. QUANTITY: adapt to the growing occurrence of drought and floods linked to climate change

- The Prut River is the main source of surface water. Thus, the multiannual average flow for Prut River in the period 1945 - 2016 was 82.5 m³/s. In the last 7 years, however, there has been a decrease in average flows of about 20 m³/s, which can be explained by the increased anthropic pressure on the Prut basin in the mountain region (through deforestation, riverblocks and construction of hydroelectric power stations etc.). Surface water reserves (small rivers and tributaries of the Prut River) are estimated at 737.3 million m³ and they are used as technological water at local level;
- Groundwater currently provides 70% of the overall water needs. Following the hydrogeological prospects, total groundwater reserves were estimated to be 3,478.9 m³/day on 01.01.2014. Natural background concentrations of salinity indices (Cl, SO₄, Na, TDS, etc.) are quite high, because of the marine origin of water-bearing sediments, which still contain saline waters in their pores;

- Institutional capacities for water resources management should be improved by creating appropriate territorial structures, i.e. districts and basin committees, with a decision-making role;
- The priority should be water bodies with water overuse or potential flood risk and developing concrete actions to be implemented.

9.4. ECOSYSTEMS: benefit from the services of a healthy environment

- Underwater land occupies only 1.9% of the district surface. The largest surfaces with lakes are in the lower valley of the Prut River (Beleu and Manta). Wetlands are of great importance and need to be preserved. Beyond their crucial role for biodiversity, they offer a significant buffer in the context of climate change;
- The lower Prut lakes region is included in the List of Wetlands of International Importance, as Ramsar area No. 1029 “Lower Prut Lakes” (especially as a habitat for aquatic birds);
- Hydromorphological monitoring, which does not currently exist, should be implemented;
- Special attention should be given to permanent vegetalisation of river banks and the development of trees beside the river to reduce pollution and evaporation;
- Interruption of lateral and longitudinal connectivity affects the reproduction of some fish species. Flood defences in particular and more widely man-made infrastructures in the riverbed should be rethought and replaced by potential nature-based solutions.

9.5. GOVERNANCE FOR EFFICIENT WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

- The first RBMP cycle (for the period 2018-2023) for the DPBS RBD was approved through the Government Decision No. 955 on 3 October 2018. It is proposed to use the opportunity to prepare an upgraded second cycle and synchronize it with all the Danube countries and European

Member States. This 2nd plan has thus been prepared to be adopted before the implementation period of December 2021 – December 2027 in line with the WFD;

- Lack of implementation mechanisms for the existing legal acts; there are not applied or enforced sufficiently;
- Implementation of the differentiated tariff in water consumption;
- “Apele Moldovei” Agency is responsible for coordinating the participative RBM Planning and management of surface water resources; an improvement in data management to improve available knowledge and stakeholder awareness is key for sustainable improvement along the planning cycles.
- The monitoring of groundwater resources comes under the jurisdiction of the AGRM and surface water comes under the Environmental Agency; In order to tackle the challenge of monitoring in line with EU standards, groundwater and surface water bodies have been redefined.

10. LEGISLATIVE AND INSTITUTIONAL CONTEXT

10.1. Latest legal development of importance for RBMP

The Republic of Moldova, as an EU associated country, has a responsibility to harmonise its water legislation in line with the EU WFD. The main aim of the EU WFD consists in reaching the good status of all waters by preventing deterioration and ensuring long-term sustainability of water uses. WFD further provides an innovative approach in terms of a water resources management approach based on river basins, taking into account the natural boundaries of the watershed.

At the national level, adaptation and harmonisation of the EU WFD is reflected in the Water Law of the Republic of Moldova that was adopted on 23.12.2011 and enforced on 26.10.2013. Thus, the objectives of both the WFD and the Water Law of the Republic of Moldova lie in RBMP development and implementation.

The first cycle of the RBMP for the DPBS RBD was approved through Government Decision No. 955 on 3 October 2018.

10.2. Competent authority and institutions for water management & stakeholder involvement

For the implementation of RBMPs, the MARDE is responsible for developing action plans for each of its subdivisions. Within the Ministry, the person responsible for the implementation of the Plan is the head of the Integrated Water Resources Management Policy, Mr. Adrian Delinschi. Thus, the “Apele Moldovei” Agency and District Committee “Basin Water

Management Authority”, in the person of Mr. Proca Dumitru, the head of the Water Resources Management Department, are responsible for the management of surface water resources, and the AGRM is responsible for the management of groundwater resources. The implementation of the surface water monitoring (quantitative monitoring) is ensured by SHS, and sources of pollution are controlled by the Environmental Agency. The protection, monitoring of water quality for drinking water, abstraction, water-related leisure and recreation areas are performed by the National Agency for Public Health and local Public Health Centers under the Ministry of Health, Labour and Social Protection.

At the end of 2017, the DPBS RBD Committee was created. This body has a coordination and advisory function and is actively involved in efficient water resources management. The Committee consists of representatives from central and local public administration authorities, sub-committees, water user associations, civil and the scientific society. The Committee meets every six months.

11. SUMMARY OF THE FIRST CONSULTATION

Until the first week of August, the National Environmental Center organized **5 public consultations** in 5 regions of Moldova: **Edinet, Hîncești, Falești, Comrat** and **Cahul** with the participation of over 170 people, mayors, representatives from Rayon Councils, Environment Protection Inspection (EPI), Public Health Centre (PHC), water users, NGOs etc.

1. HANCESTI DISTRICT 12TH JULY 2019
2. EDINET DISTRICT16TH JULY 2019
3. FALESTI DISTRICT23RD JULY 2019
4. CAHUL DISTRICT 30TH JULY 2019
- 5 COMRAT DISTRICT..... 30TH JULY 2019

The experts within the public dialogues that interacted with the audience answering to the questions were the following:

Dr. Conf. Iurii Bejan, deputy director, Institute of Ecology and Geography

Mrs. Mariana Codreanu, Specialist Principal, Department of Water Resources Management

Mr. Dumitru Proca, Head of Department of Water Resources Management

Mrs. Ina Coseru, Chair of the National Environmental Center

Mrs. Iuliana Cantaragiu, Project Expert at the National Environmental Center

The content of each meeting was structured in the following order:

1. Introductory part about EUWI+ projects, explanation of potential impact, importance of conducting analysis and the expected results with deliverables in their order.

2. The scientific part was covered by Mr. Iurie Bejan based on reports crafted by Environment Agency in collaboration with Academy of Science, Statistics Bureau and Public Health Centre. The data for each district apart to increase relevance, spur engagement and offer comparison space for better reflection.

Afterwards, the meeting was accompanied by discussions. Participants expressed their views on the main identified water issues of the basin and filled out questionnaires.

The results were encoded in reactions targeting precise issues, for example: The head of EPI Briceni region, spoke with a warning note that the orchards are planted in Briceni at an exaggerated rate, which triggers massive pesticides usage (15 or even 26 times), thus the pressure on the ecosystem and the quality of the water is drastically diminished, representing a great danger to the public health as well.

A representative of the local NGO (Falesti) promoting ecological agriculture proposed: conducting population awareness campaigns (invoking the fact that, no matter how strange it may sound, people are simply not fully aware of the water resources dynamics in their own region); increasing and tightening environmental control measures; improvement of good agricultural practices (use of organic fertilizers) and monitoring of rivers.

Certainly, the most frequent and sensitive questions were:

- Elaboration of regulations for water bodies,
- Insufficient human resources specialized in the environment in the city halls and
- Financial coverage of potential projects.

All reactions were conveyed to the DPBSR District Committee for further analysis and inclusion into the management plan.

12. SUMMARY OF THE SECOND CONSULTATION

Within September 15-19th, 4 sessions of public consultation were organised to present the Programme of Measures of the draft Danube-Prut & Black Sea River Basin Management Plan developed with support of the European Union Water Initiative + (EUWI+). The second consultation meeting on Danube-Prut and Black Sea RBMP in Republic of Moldova has gathered 66 participants including the representatives of beneficiary institutions, regional and local authorities, NGOs, etc.

The consultations were held as follows:

- **September 15th** in Briceni with participants from Briceni and Edinet districts,
- **September 15th** in Balti with participants from Balti, Falesti, Glodeni and Rîscani districts,
- **September 19th** in Nisporeni with participants from Nisporeni and Ungheni districts,
- **September 19th** in Hîncesti with participants from Hîncesti and Leova districts.

66 participants attended the 4 public consultations, most of them being the mayors of the localities from the mentioned districts, the representatives of the Water-Canal Authority, the civil society, farmers. The management plan was presented to the participants, later they will receive by e-mail the presentation of the plan and will send in return 3 priorities identified specific to their locality.

The second thematic summary of the current findings on environmental objectives and Programme of measures has been prepared and Danube-Prut and Black Sea factsheet has been updated for the meeting.

THE RESULTS

Most participants highlighted the lack of water. One of the discussed problems is the water and the ponds that catch water that do not allow farmers to use water for irrigation, because after gathering the fish, the water is discharged. Some of the mayors came up with the idea of drafting a regulation for the lease of ponds. This regulation would regulate the relationship between the owner and the lessor, it would include conditions of water use.

Other participants came with the experience of winning projects in the field and recommended the creation of local NGOs to attract funds.

THE NEED TO INVEST IN WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANTS AND MODERNISATION OF SEWERAGE SYSTEM

The participants also listed the problem of wastewater discharge, dumping waste in river waters, lack of water due to drought and among its solutions they see the construction of treatment plants, construction and modernization of sewerage systems, implementation of legislation and thorough verification by the Environmental Protection Inspectorate of sources of river pollution.

TIMETABLE AND WORK PLAN UP TO THE ADOPTION OF THE RBMP

The RBMP was developed for the implementation period 2022 – 2027. The plan was developed during the period July 2018 - November 2020. The first round of public consultations took place between April and September 2019. The results of these consultations were used in the elaboration of the Program of Measures.

The second round of consultations will start in June 2020 and will last until the end of the year, when the process of adopting the Plan will begin and the EUWI + project will be completed. The plan must be adopted by December 2021, to be implemented in the period 2022-2027.

TECHNICAL REPORTS

The following technical reports are part of RBMP, giving the background information used to feed the different chapters:

Technical Report N°1: presents the analysis of the general characterisation of the DPBS RBD.

Technical Report N°2: presents driving forces, types of pressures and their impact on the quality and quantity of water resources in DPBS RBD. Surface waters were analysed at water body level, and the groundwater was analysed at groundwater body level (according to the new delineation).

Technical Report N°3: presents the description of protected areas according to the WFD (identification and mapping of protected areas).

Technical Report N°4: Surface and groundwater water monitoring assessment report.

Technical Report N°5: presents the environmental objective for SWBs, GWBs and protected areas.

Technical Report N°6: presents the economic analysis of water use in the DPBS RBD.

Technical Report N°7: presents the Programme of Measures.

Technical Report N°8: Public information and consultation measures taken when developing the RBMP.

DATA SOURCES

The primary sources of information used for the current diagnostic analysis come from the following sources: the first cycle of the RBMP for DPBS RBD, delineation reports, mapping and classification of groundwater bodies, cartographic material (orthophotoplans, maps at a scale of 1:50 000), statistical data collected from the National Bureau of Statistics (statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Moldova (1990-2018)), State Ecological Inspectorate (State Ecological Inspectorate Yearbooks (2007-2018)), SHS and Environmental Agency (Yearbooks with monitoring data on water quality and quantity (2012-2018)) and “Apele Moldovei” Agency (Report No.1 on Water Management, “Apele Moldovei” Agency (1990-2018)). Main data sources used have been gathered a catalogue of data sources available on-line.

13. PROCEDURES FOR OBTAINING THE TECHNICAL REPORTS

No	Report title	Available from
1	General characterisation, Danube Prut Black Sea	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/840-moldova-technical-report-1-general-characterisation-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?fromsearch=1
2	Analysis of pressures and impacts on water resources and evaluation of the risk of non-achieving the environmental objectives	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/841-moldova-technical-report-2-pressures-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?fromsearch=1
3	Protected areas	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/842-moldova-technical-report-3-protected-areas-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?fromsearch=1
4	Surface and groundwater monitoring in the Danube-Prut and Black Sea river basin district	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/843-moldova-technical-report-4-monitoring-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?fromsearch=1
5	Environmental objectives	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/844-moldova-technical-report-5-environmental-objectives-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?-fromsearch=1

No	Report title	Available from
6	Economic analysis of water use	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/845-moldova-technical-report-6-economic-analysis-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?fromsearch=1
7	Programme of measures	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/846-moldova-technical-report-7-programme-of-measures-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?fromsearch=1
8	Public information and consultation measures	https://www.euwipluseast.eu/en/component/k2/item/847-moldova-technical-report-8-1st-public-consultations-danube-prut-black-sea-ro?-fromsearch=1

GLOSSARY

Impacts	The environmental effect of pressure (poor quality of water resources)
Monitoring	Assessment of the quality and quantity of the surface or ground water resources
Pressures	The direct effect of the drive , e.g. an effect that causes a change in flow or a change in the water chemistry
Protected areas according to WFD	Areas requiring special protection under WFD and other EC Directives and waters used for the abstraction of drinking water
RBMP	River Basin Management Plan, territorial planning document: it gives the overall orientations of water management in the basin and the objectives to be reached, the delay and the priority actions to be developed for a defined period of tim
Status	Condition of a water body resulting from natural and anthropogenic factors (= potential). It can be High, Good, Moderate, Poor, or Bad
Water balance	The relation of water inflo , outflow and accumulation (change of storage) in any river basin or water body in a given period (year, month, decade and other)
Water bodies	Homogeneous natural hydrological basic unit or volume of groundwater within an aquifer
Water resources	Sources of water that are useful or potentially useful to humans

